

Formation of Complex Compounds between Lead nitrate Potassium nitrate

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Earlier work¹ on measurements of viscosity, parachor, magnetic susceptibility etc., indicates the formation of complex compounds $XKNO_3 \cdot Pb(NO_3)_2$ where $X = 1, 2$ and 4 , when aq. solutions of lead nitrate and potassium nitrate are mixed together. Transport number measurements point out to the existence of a compound $K_4[Pb(NO_3)_6]$ corresponding to $X = 4$.

Raman spectrum of a solution containing this compound is compared below with that of $Pb(NO_3)_2$ solution.

Exciting line	$Pb(NO_3)_2$	$4KNO_3 \cdot Pb(NO_3)_2$
λ 4358	$\Delta\nu$ 1055.5	$\Delta\nu$ 1064.4
λ 4046	$\Delta\nu$ 1052.7	$\Delta\nu$ 1060.7

The difference in frequency shifts is nearly 9 cm^{-1} and appears to be too small to suggest the formation of the complex compound $K_4[Pb(NO_3)_6]$ as proposed.

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